

MultiXscale

Dissemination and Communication Plan

MultiXscale Deliverable 7.1
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MultiXscale
EuroHPC Centre of Excellence for
Multiscale Modelling

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Joint Undertaking

Acknowledgement

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Project and Deliverable Information

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Executive Summary

The deliverable here presented describes the branding of MultiXscale project as well as the dissemination strategy to be followed alongside the duration of the project.

The target audience of MultiXscale project is quite heterogeneous:

- Industrialists (including small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)), in particular in the areas:
 - Software vendors.
 - Material and life sciences industries.
 - Cloud providers.
 - HPC professional services.
- Academics, in particular:
 - Senior scientists.
 - Post-docs and students.
- Research software developers (both industrial and academic).
- EU-funded initiatives linked to HPC: other CoEs, PRACE, ETP4HPC, EuroHPC, ESFRI, etc.
- Hardware vendors and system integrators.
- Funding agencies, interest groups, policy makers and political stakeholders.
- General public.

As a result, it is key to find the correct channels to use for dissemination purposes. Each dissemination channel used addresses different subgroups of the target audience. Some examples of these include:

- Conference-style events, such as:
 - EuroHPC Summit Week which targets other EuroHPC projects, hardware vendors, funding agencies,
 - ISC High Performance which targets Cloud providers, HPC professionals, research software developers, hardware vendors,
 - ESPResSo School on Engineering Materials which targets domain-specific academic users.
- Press releases and newsletters:
 - In domain publications such as HPCwire and InsideHPC,
 - For a general audience, for example national media press releases and conferences such as that held for Slovenian media at the project kick-off event.
- Publications in scientific journals to target academic and industrial scientists.
- A scientific comic to explain the activities connected to MultiXscale for a general audience.

In addition, the content and aesthetics of the external documentation and social network publications should be carefully considered, as it is described in this document.

This deliverable starts with an introduction of the dissemination team, a list of objectives to fulfil during the 48 months of the project, a description of the branding elements behind MultiXscale, the dissemination tools and channels, and a latter section where the monitoring and KPI of the project are described. Additionally, a list with all the past and scheduled events since the beginning of the project will be provided, as well as an updated list of news published both by members of the consortium and external journals. The deliverable connects each of these dissemination tools and channels to the target audience that they are intended to reach.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

This deliverable contains all the elements relevant to dissemination and communication, including branding elements, document templates, future activities and definition of key performance indicators:

- Introduction to the dissemination team, list of goals, internal communication guidelines and target audiences (Section 2).
- Branding elements, including the logo, slides and deliverable templates, plus the acknowledgement and disclaimer sentences which should be included in the dissemination material (Section 3).
- Dissemination tools and channels such as website, social media, past and future events, dissemination material, press strategy and press releases (Section 4).
- Monitoring and KPIs, including a list of the KPIs of the project and its current status at month three (Section 5).

1.1.1 Target audience

The recommendations of this deliverable are targeted at the members of the MultiXscale project, who have to strictly follow the branding guidelines and template elements. Additionally, the content of this deliverable may be useful to the general public due to the enumeration of the communication channel and dissemination activities.

2 Organization

2.1 Dissemination team

Dissemination activities and communication plan belong to Work Package (WP) 7 entitled *Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication*. WP7 leader (HPCNow!) is the Dissemination Coordinator. HPCNow! is responsible for ensuring that dissemination tasks are fulfilled in a timely and effective manner. The Dissemination Coordinator will maintain a close relationship with the management and technical boards and the project participants to ensure continuous and coherent dissemination.

The dissemination team is completed with the members of the National Institute of Chemistry, Universitat de Barcelona and Leonardo. These entities participate in different tasks of WP7.

2.2 Objectives

The main objectives of the dissemination team are:

- To increase awareness of extreme scale computing, in particular within the EuroHPC JU ecosystem, and demonstrate its effectiveness as an enabling factor in industry, academia and to the general public.
- Expand the user base of High Performance Computing (HPC) technologies in the domain.
- Endorse the role of extreme scale computing as an enabler of societal benefits through the advancement of multiscale research.
- Promote the solutions and services put in place by MultiXscale to support the target communities of application developers and users in their adoption of, and adaptation to, an increasingly complex research computing environment.

2.3 Internal communication

Effective and efficient internal communication is key to fulfilling the project objectives. To guarantee the regular project workflow, the following best practices will be implemented:

- Ensure that all the partners have a holistic view of the project.
- Keep the participants of each work package involved in its activities.
- Create a secure space for shared feedback and discussions.
- Guarantee complete transparency across the different work packages.
- Prevent potential obstacles beforehand.

Internal communication refers to the use of the following channels:

- A set of mailing lists for specific groups, such as consortium members, work package leaders and steering committee, will be used to share all relevant information:
 - Finances: finance-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - General assembly: GA-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - Associate partners: associates-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - Administration: admins-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - Steering committee: SC-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - Work package leaders: WPLEaders-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
 - Dissemination team: dissemination-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si
- A Slack channel for informal discussions.
- A common online repository will be used to hold all the documentation relative to the project accessible to all members.
- Recurring teleconferences to align the technical, scientific, management and dissemination activities.

2.4 Target audiences

MultiXscale project targets a broad audience:

- Industrialists (including SMEs), in particular in the areas:
 - Software vendors.
 - Material and life sciences industries.
 - Cloud providers.
 - HPC professional services.
- Academics, in particular:
 - Senior scientists.
 - Post-docs and students.
- Research software developers (both industrial and academic).
- EU-funded initiatives linked to HPC: other CoEs, PRACE, ETP4HPC, EuroHPC, ESFRI, etc.
- Hardware vendors and system integrators.
- Funding agencies, interest groups, policy makers and political stakeholders.
- General public.

Each target audience category is addressed in ways that are considered most likely to generate traction within that category. The target audience addressed by each of the events attended or organised by MultiXscale is included in Table 1 (under Section 4).

3 Branding

The visual identity presented here will be consistent in all the dissemination, internal and external communication and reporting activities. This branding strategy provides rapid identification and recognition of the project and an internal unification of our identity.

In this section, the main elements of MultiXscale branding are presented.

3.1 Logo

The logo (Figure 1) clearly shows the name of the project (MultiXscale). The "X" letter is replaced by a representation of a four-legged chip in a running position, which represents the performance of a computational process. To show the adaptation of the project to different execution scales, the thickness of the font alongside "MultiXscale" word size decreases from "M" to "e".

Figure 1: MultiXscale logo

3.2 Templates

The Dissemination Team, in conjunction with the management team, designed and created templates (Figure 2) for internal and external communications. They will be accessible for partners to download on the project's common repository. The rationale behind this strategy is to guarantee a univocal communication style and provide the entire MultiXscale team with a shared toolkit of communication items to be deployed in recurring events.

Figure 2: MultiXscale templates: a) Slide deck for Microsoft PowerPoint, b) Deliverable template in Overleaf.

3.2.1 Microsoft PowerPoint templates for slides

The template for MultiXscale slides contains the following elements, from top to bottom and from left to right (see Figure 2a). For title slide:

- MultiXscale logo.
- European Union logo followed by “Co-founded by the European Union”.
- EuroHPC Joint Undertaking logo.
- The sentence “EuroHPC Centre of Excellence”.
- Presentation title.
- Name and surname of the presenter, and her/his institution.
- Date of presentation.
- Disclaimer sentence.

For the last slide:

- MultiXscale logo.
- European Union logo followed by “Co-founded by the European Union” and EuroHPC Joint Undertaking logo.
- Web page, Facebook and Twitter account names for MultiXscale.
- The logo of the sixteen participants in MultiXscale project.
- Acknowledgement sentence.

3.2.2 Overleaf template for Deliverables

Deliverables will be written in LaTeX following the same template (see Figure 2b). The main page of the deliverable template contains the following elements:

- MultiXscale logo.
- Title of the deliverable
- Deliverable number, type and date.
- Project title.
- European Union logo followed by “Co-founded by the European Union” and EuroHPC Joint Undertaking logo.
- Acknowledgement sentence.
- Disclaimer sentence.

The second page of the deliverable includes general information about the project and deliverable, containing information about the project, the EuroHPC Project Officer, and information about the deliverable (ID, nature, dissemination level, date of delivery and description), plus the document keywords and the disclaimer and copyright notices. The content of the deliverable itself starts on the third page with the table of contents. All deliverables will include an executive summary and an introduction section, containing the scope of the deliverable and the target audience. The last page will include the references: acronyms used, URLs referenced and any citations.

3.3 Publication of acknowledgement sentence and disclaimer

All the documentation generated during the project (deliverables, presentations, dissemination and communication materials, etc.), should contain an acknowledgement and disclaimer sentences, which are listed below:

3.3.1 Acknowledgement sentence

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and countries participating in the project under grant agreement No 101093169.

3.3.2 Disclaimer sentence

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) and countries participating in the project. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

4 Dissemination tools and channels

MultiXscale project includes a varied list of dissemination tools and channels, which are listed below.

4.1 Website

The URL of the project website is <https://www.multixscale.eu/>. It will be the central part of the dissemination activities and the face of the project, covering the entire spectrum of target audiences (see Section 2.4). The website will be updated regularly, according to the new content (deliverables, news items, tweets, etc.)

Figure 3: Main page of MultiXscale website

4.2 Social media

Additionally to the website, the project information is also disseminated using social media (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Screenshots of the headers of the four social networks used in MultiXscale project taken on 28th March 2023. a) Twitter, b) Youtube, c) Facebook and d) LinkedIn.

Four specific profiles have been created:

- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/MultiXscale>
- Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@MultiXscale>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/people/MultiXscale/100090773041074/>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/multixscale/>

The accounts will be used to inform the audience about new publications, deliverables, presentations and events. The socializing events and other spontaneous publications will be only shared via Twitter.

4.3 Events

A complete dissemination of the project should include participation in different events, both at technical and scientific levels. MultiXscale will also participate in large supercomputing conferences such as the SC conference series in the United States and ISC High Performance, which takes place in Germany, considering its participation in shared booths in collaboration with project partners or other European projects.

In Table 1 the past, scheduled and planned events to disseminate MultiXscale project to the date of 31st March 2023 are shown.

Status	Name	Location	Date	Target
Past	EuroHPC Summit week 2023	Goteborg (Sweden)	20-23 March 2023	Other EuroHPC projects, hardware vendors, funding agencies
Scheduled	Easybuild user meeting	London (UK)	24-26 April 2023	Academics and industrial users
Scheduled	HPCKP Meeting	Barcelona (Spain)	17-18 May 2023	Academics and industrial users
Scheduled	ISC High Performance	Hamburg (Germany)	21-25 May 2023	Cloud providers, HPC professionals, research software developers, hardware vendors
Scheduled	Sysadmin-focused tutorial on CVMFS	Online	Autumn (TBD)	EuroHPC JU system administrators
Planned	Supercomputing HUST'23 workshop	Denver (US)	12-17 Nov. 2023	Users and HPC professionals
Planned	Espresso School on Engineering Materials	TBD	Fall (TBD)	Academic users

Table 1: List of past, scheduled and future events to disseminate MultiXscale project.

4.4 Poster

EuroHPC JU kindly offered us to present our project in a poster (Figure 5) during the EuroHPC Summit Week 23 which took place in Goteborg past March. The poster was presented by Alan Ó Cais and Thomas Röblitz. A digital copy of the poster can be found on the [MultiXscale website](#) and in the [EuroHPC Summit website](#), poster number 32.

4.5 Dissemination material

A proper way to arrive at the audience is by providing physical elements properly labelled with MultiXscale branding elements. To do so, some dissemination material was manufactured and distributed during EuroHPC Summit week and the MultiXscale kick-off meeting. In the near future, more units and variety of goods will be manufactured to be distributed in future events. To the date, 70 units of postcards and stickers, and 50 units of pens, mugs and tote bags have been distributed (Figure 6).

4.6 Press releases and newsletters

Press releases will be issued and distributed periodically, and included in the newsletter to be published twice per year (every 6 months). The press releases published until the drafting of this deliverable are:

- MultiXscale project was already mentioned in the [press release launched by EuroHPC](#) (26th January 2023).
- Same press released also published in [HPCwire portal](#) (26th January 2023).
- Announcement of the grant awarded to MultiXscale project published by the coordinator, NIC, on its [website](#) and in [HPCNow! website](#) (26th January 2023).
- Further information about the kick-off meeting, carried out from 23rd to 24th March, was covered by [local media](#) [in Slovenian] (23rd March 2023).

Figure 5: Poster presented at EuroHPC Summit week 2023. Goteborg (Sweden).

Figure 6: Dissemination material distributed to the date.

To highlight, there was a press conference organized 23rd March during the first day of the kick-off meeting at the National Institute of Chemistry in Ljubljana, Slovenia. Several journalists from different media were invited to this event, presented by Matej Praprotnik, the project coordinator.

The articles listed here below were published after the press conference:

- Slovenian supercomputer contribution to solving globally important issues (*Slovenski superračunalniški prispevek k reševanju svetovno pomembnih vprašanj*) [in Slovenian]. Published also [here](#) [in Slovene].
- Photo service *Napoved - fotoservis, 23. 3. (četrtek)* [in Slovenian]
- New MultiXscale Center of Excellence at Chemistry Institute to Accelerate Transition to Supercomputing Resources (*Nov Center odličnosti MultiXscale na kemijskem inštitutu za pospešitev prehoda na superračunalniške vire*) [in Slovenian]
- [Chemistry Institute spearheading EUR 6m multiscale simulation project.](#)
- The Institute of Chemistry presented the MultiXscale program today (*Kemijski inštitut danes predstavil program MultiXscale*) [in Slovenian].
- [Press conference of the Institute of Chemistry](#)

4.7 Press strategy

Press releases, announcements and relevant information produced by MultiXscale project will be sent periodically for publication to specialized magazines and portals such as:

- [HPCwire](#)
- [insideHPC](#)
- [The Next Platform](#)
- [Scientific Computing World](#)

Besides, representatives of MultiXscale project attending the events mentioned above will take advantage of the networking sessions organized with journalists to transmit the achievements of the project to reach the target audience. This approach is also specifically serve the "general public" target audience.

All the press impacts registered will be available on the website of the project.

4.8 Publication in scientific journals

Results obtained during the MultiXscale project will be submitted for publication to top-level peer-reviewed international journals. The partners have preidentified a list of journals in which publications could be presented:

- Journal of Chemical Physics (Impact factor (2022): 4.304)
- Computer Physics Communications (Impact factor (2022): 4.717)
- Journal of Chemical Theory and Communication (Impact factor (2023): 6.578)
- Journal of Computational Physics (Impact factor (2022): 4.645)

4.9 Comic

The E-CAM HPC Centre of Excellence, which can be considered the predecessor project to MultiXscale, created a comic, [Ekham the Wise](#), in order to make itself more accessible to the wider general public (see Fig. 7). This approach was seen to be quite successful, and the comic continues to generate positive feedback nearly two years after the end of the project (for example, appearing at a number of comic conventions).

MultiXscale intends to adopt the same approach, producing a project-specific scientific comic during the second reporting period that explains, in an accessible way to a general audience, the activities of the project.

Figure 7: Ekham the Wise scientific comic created by the E-CAM HPC Centre of Excellence

5 Monitoring and KPIs

5.1 MultiXscale dissemination KPIs

A set of key indicators has been established in order to ensure that the dissemination activities are correctly targeted and, if needed, updated. These indicators will be used in order to measure progress towards achieving the dissemination objectives and to allow WP7 to steer dissemination activities in the right direction. Indicators include website visitors, social network followers, number of press impacts, number of workshops and events, etc. Table 2 below summarizes the key performance indicators identified and contains the current status after three months of operation:

Measure	Objective	Target audience	KPIs (M48)	KPIs (M3)
Visual identity and communication	Highlight project goals towards targeted groups	Scientific community, companies, general public	Distributed promo materials (500). Events attended (20)	70 promo material distributed. 1 event attended.
Website	Increase visibility. Promotion. Tool to spread information	General public	2500 visits, 500 downloads, 1000 views of clips	Website created
Conferences, round tables, thematic events	Raise awareness among the scientific and industry community	Scientific community	7 articles submitted	No articles submitted yet
Social media	Increasing the visibility of the project	Scientific community, general public	300 followers on each social media. 1000 views of video clips	Followers/Subscribers Facebook (7), Twitter (12), LinkedIn (12), Youtube (21)
Press releases, newsletters and press conferences	Create awareness about the project goals and targeted outcomes	Media, scientific community, policy makers, industry, general public	20 media representatives attending press events, 10 published media articles	1 mention in HPCwire, 3 media representatives at press conference, 5 published media articles, 1 national TV news item

Table 2: MultiXscale KPIs description and current status

5.2 Continuous reporting

Continuous reporting activities will be performed throughout the project lifetime concerning the dissemination activities. This process will allow a constant evaluation of the project's progression. WP7 will be required to report continuously based on the timing and conditions agreed with the granting authority. The reporting will be performed on the European Funding and Tenders Portal, in the "Manage project" section.

References

Acronyms Used

HPC High Performance Computing
SMEs small and medium-sized enterprises
WP Work Package

URLs referenced

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<https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables> ... <https://www.multixscale.eu/deliverables>
Internal Project Management Link ... <https://github.com/orgs/multixscale/projects/1>
elisabeth.ortega@hpcnow.com ... <mailto:elisabeth.ortega@hpcnow.com>
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dissemination-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si ... dissemination-MultiXscale@cmm.ki.si

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<https://twitter.com/MultiXscale> ... <https://twitter.com/MultiXscale>
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